

Open Biomedical Ontologies Applied to Prostate Cancer

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Abstract

This paper surveys preliminary results from the Interdisciplinary Prostate Ontology Project (IPOP), in which ontologies from the Open Biomedical Ontologies (OBO) library have been used to annotate clinical reports about prostate cancer. First we discuss why we rejected several controlled vocabularies, including SNOMED, DICOM, and RadLex, preferring instead to use the OBO library. We then briefly describe the database-backed website we have created around the relevant OBO ontologies, and provide excerpts of reports from radiology, surgery, and pathology which we have hyperlinked to the ontology terms. This method allows us to discover which relevant terms exist in the OBO library, and which do not. The final section of this paper discusses these gaps in the OBO library and considers methods of filling them.

Introduction

The Interdisciplinary Prostate Ontology Project aims to develop expertise with biomedical ontologies at the University of Western Ontario and the London Health Sciences Centre. This paper surveys results from the first stage of IPOP, which assessed existing biomedical ontology tools and applied them to clinical reporting about prostate cancer.

The main goal of IPOP is to improve communication between medical practitioners from radiology, oncology, anatomy, surgery, pathology, and other areas. Communication is often impeded by local variations in the use of terminology. Controlled vocabularies are part of the solution to this problem. Biomedical ontologies improve upon controlled vocabularies by linking together terms and thus allowing for better computerized data collection, search, and analysis. We hope that improving communication will ultimately lead to better patient outcomes¹.

Our first step was to assess different approaches to ontologies and controlled vocabularies. For reasons discussed below, we rejected controlled vocabularies including SNOMED CT, DICOM, and RadLex. Our preferred alternative is to use ontologies from the Open Biomedical Ontologies consortium, and in particular from their OBO Foundry initiative. OBO

includes a network of well designed, interoperable ontologies, which cover a wide range of relevant terminology.

We then created a database-backed website around the relevant OBO ontologies. Each ontology term has a web page describing it and linking it to parent and child terms via relations like “is_a” and “part_of”. We collected examples of radiology, surgery, and pathology reports dealing with prostate cancer, added them to our website, and hyperlinked the relevant terms in those reports to terms in the database of ontologies. Our approach is designed to reveal which relevant terms already exist within the OBO ontologies and which are not yet included in any OBO ontologies. We conclude this paper by suggesting fragments of one ontology which would be useful for completing the annotation of these reports.

IPOP shares much in common with Marwede and Fielding’s recent work on ontologies in clinical radiology². Their focus is on radiology reporting, in many different forms, with a view to annotating medical images using ontology terms. Our focus is on prostate cancer across medical disciplines, but we are also interested in extending the use of ontologies to medical image annotation.

Controlled Vocabularies

We assessed several controlled vocabularies before settling on OBO ontologies. This section outlines these alternatives and our reasons for setting them aside.

SNOMED CT

Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine -- Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) is a very large collection of medical terms which is becoming widely used throughout the world. The chief advantage of SNOMED is its broad coverage of terms describing medical practice. But SNOMED has been criticized for not following sound ontological theory³, and for including many errors of classification⁴. OBO and many Semantic Web systems show that a network of specialized tools is often more flexible and comprehensive in the long run than centralized and monolithic approaches like SNOMED.

DICOM

Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) is an industry driven standard for medical imaging files, their storage, and their transmission over networks. The DICOM Structured Reporting standard (DICOM-SR) extends DICOM to the kinds of textual reports considered in the first stage of IPOP⁵. DICOM covers many terms important for our future work on medical image annotation. But DICOM-SR is not yet in wide use, and since the terms defined in “DICOM Part 16: Content Mapping Resource” are largely derived from SNOMED, for our current purposes they share the same problems.

RadLex

The Radiology Lexicon (RadLex) is a controlled vocabulary developed by the Radiology Society of North America (RSNA). There are ongoing efforts to transform RadLex from a lexicon into an ontology⁶, and to reduce its duplication of other more comprehensive ontologies like the Foundational Model of Anatomy (FMA)⁷.

OBO Ontologies

Each of the preceding tools has its strengths. In particular, they share a focus on the practice of medicine and medical interventions. However our group has chosen to pursue an alternative approach.

The Open Biomedical Ontologies library includes a large number ontology projects, and the OBO Foundry initiative aims to unite them under a set of shared best practices⁸. Each OBO Foundry ontology is specialized for a particular domain and designed by a group of experts in the relevant field. When two domains overlap, the goal is keep their ontologies separate but link them together, creating a division of labour.

Advantages of the OBO Foundry ontologies include permissive licenses, open source practices, a human-readable common file format, and a shared Basic Formal Ontology (BFO). Although many of the OBO ontologies are incomplete, and although there are many domains relevant to IPOP which are not yet covered by OBO, in our assessment the OBO Foundry approach is the best bet for future work in biomedical ontologies.

Below we describe in brief some of the OBO ontologies which we have found useful for our goal of annotating clinical reports about prostate cancer in humans.

- Foundational Model of Anatomy (FMA): provides IPOP with terms such as FMA:9600

“prostate”, as well as terms for the parts of the prostate and its neighbouring organs.

- Disease Ontology (DO/DOID): parallels the structure of the FMA and describes diseases of various portion of the human anatomy. For IPOP the main terms of interest are DOID:47 “prostate disease” and its children, including DOID:514 “prostatic neoplasms” and DOID:8634 “carcinoma in situ of prostate”.
- Protein Ontology (PRO): proteins like prostate specific antigen (PSA) are important for the detection of prostate cancer.
- Gene Ontology (GO): provides terms related to PSA, such as GO:0004252 “serine-type endopeptidase activity” and GO:0016525 “negative regulation of angiogenesis”.
- Phenotype Quality (PATO): designed to describe phenotypes of organisms, it contains many terms useful for qualitative assessments in general. Relevant to IPOP are the children of the term PATO:0000014 “color” used in biopsies, as well as terms for patterns (e.g. PATO:0000060 “spatial pattern”) and textures (e.g. PATO:0000701 “smooth”).
- Units of Measurement (UO): organizes the International System of Units (SI) into an ontology, and includes other terms such as UO:0000190 “ratio”.

Annotating Reports

In the first stage of IPOP our focus has been on annotating the text of clinical reports using ontology terms. These three samples come from reports on three separate patients. A selection of OBO terms is marked in bold and explained.

Radiology Report Sample

“**Peripheral Zone**: This zone is relatively homogeneous with a **smooth contour** although it is compressed by a large **transition zone**.”

- “peripheral zone” corresponds to FMA:19587 “peripheral zone of prostate”
- “smooth” is PATO:0000701
- “contour” corresponds to PATO:0000052 “shape”
- “transition zone” corresponds to FMA:45721 “transition zone of prostate”

Surgery Report Sample

“Once the **prostate** was mobilized in a cephalad direction, I could see **Denonvilliers fascia**. This was opened in the midline. We then dissected out the **ampulla of Vater**, which were clipped and divided. The **seminal vesicles** were dissected off in their entirety quite easily using clips for **hemostasis**.”

- “prostate” is FMA:9600
- “Denonvilliers fascia” is a synonym for FMA:19933 “rectovesical septum”
- “ampulla of Vater” is a synonym for FMA:15076 “hepatopancreatic ampulla”
- “seminal vesicle” is FMA:19386
- “hemostasis” is GO:0007599

Pathology Report Sample

“The specimen consist of 2 cores of **pale tan tissue**, the larger measures 1.3 **cm** and the smaller measures 1.1 **cm**. All **tissue** is submitted in one cassette.”

- “pale tan” is a close synonym of PATO:0001268 “desaturated brown”
- “tissue” corresponds to FMA:9637 “portion of tissue”
- “cm” is UO:0000015

Gaps in OBO Ontologies

Although the OBO ontologies provide a broad and rich source of terms which we have been able to use to annotate our reports, there are important terms which cannot be found in any of the existing ontologies. Some of these terms are included in SNOMED CT, DICOM, and RadLex, but have not yet been integrated into the OBO library. In many cases these gaps reflect the focus of SNOMED CT, DICOM, and RadLex on medical practice and interventions, while OBO ontologies tend to focus on biomedical investigations.

Near Synonyms

As might be expected, there are phrases used in the reports which do not match the name of any term in an OBO ontology, nor any of the synonyms given, but are clearly meant to refer to an existing term. The example above of “pale tan” is one such case. Since our reports are annotated by human beings and not automatically, it is possible to discern the author’s intent in most cases and add the hyperlink. Variation in synonyms poses a problem for automatic annotation methods.

Missing Composites

There are UO terms for density, including “milligram per milliliter”, but no term for “nanogram per milliliter” used in PSA measurements. This points to an issue of compositionality in UO which is shared by other ontologies: not all possible combinations of terms are included in the ontology. This can be remedied either by adding the composite term to the ontology, or by using two ontology terms linked together by a well-defined relation.

Conflicting Fiat Boundaries

Ontologies like FMA include *bona fide* boundaries like those between bones and between organs, as

well as *fiat* boundaries drawn for the sake of convenience. While there tends to be good agreement about *bona fide* boundaries, it is easy to find disagreements about how fiat boundaries should be established.

For instance, the FMA divides the regional parts of FMA:9600 “prostate” into the anterior, posterior, right lateral, and left lateral lobes. Each of these lobes is given its own child terms for fibromuscular stroma, vasculature, neural network, and parenchyma. But RadLex divides the prostate’s RID:344 “anterior fibromuscular stroma” into outer and inner glands, and then into peripheral, central, and transition zones. Since prostate tumours are much more common in the peripheral zone of the prostate, it is more natural to use the RadLex nomenclature than the FMA fiat boundaries when dealing with prostate cancer. Including two distinct sets of fiat boundaries is likely to be problematic, as is mapping a set of fiat boundaries in one ontology onto a different set in another ontology.

Medical Procedures

OBO does not currently include ontologies for describing the medical procedures relevant to IPOP. Also missing are terms for the tools used to perform these procedures. For instance: digital rectal exam, transrectal ultrasound; biopsy, specimen, core, fragment, cassette; surgery, mobilize, dissect, clips.

There are ontologies being developed like the Ontology for Biomedical Investigations (OBI) which may fill some of these gaps. Investigations are, of course, distinct from interventions, and the latter is the primary concern of IPOP.

If no existing ontologies can be found to fill these gaps, the alternative is to coordinate with others to create a new ontology for these terms using OBO Foundry best practices, and submit it to the OBO consortium.

Image Types

Important for the radiological aspects of IPOP is an ontology for medical image types. Below is a proposed fragment of an “is_a” hierarchy for types of medical image.

- Medical Image
 - Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) Image
 - T1 Weighted MRI Image
 - MRI Image without Contrast
 - MRI Image with Contrast
 - Static Contrast MRI Image
 - Dynamic Contrast MRI Image

- T2 Weighted MRI Image
 - Proton Density Weighted MRI Image
 - Diffusion MRI Image
- Ultrasound (US) Image
 - A Mode US Image
 - B Mode US Image
 - Conventional US Image
 - US Image with Contrast
 - Doppler US Image
 - Power Doppler US Image
 - Colour Doppler US Image
 - Pulse Doppler US Image
 - M Mode US Image
- X-Ray Image
 - Computed Tomography (CT) Image
 - CT Image with Contrast
 - CT Image without Contrast
 - ...
 - Nuclear Medicine Image
 - ...

RadLex and DICOM contain many useful terms for medical images which could be adapted into a new ontology. It is important to maintain the distinction between medical imaging procedures and the images which are products of those procedures.

Conclusion

The first stage of IPOP has been successful in applying the OBO library to a small set of clinical reports from radiology, surgery, and pathology. The process is labour intensive, which has limited the number of cases we have annotated. Nevertheless, the small set of annotated cases will be useful as an education tool, raising awareness of the availability of ontology and the utility of controlled vocabularies. Analysis of the annotated reports has also helped us to find examples of conflicting term usage in our practice.

It is worth reiterating the difference between controlled vocabularies focused on medical practice, such as SNOMED CT, DICOM, and RadLex, and the OBO ontologies which focus on biomedical research. IPOP requires a firm foundation in biomedical science, but our goal is to improve medical practice. The evolving shared principles of the OBO Foundry promise to avoid many of the pitfalls encountered in the other controlled vocabularies. And we believe that these shared principles will prove just as fruitful in the development of new ontologies, aimed primarily at medical interventions, as they have already in developing ontologies aimed at biomedical investigations.

Our ongoing work on IPOP builds on the successes of this first stage by annotating sample reports from more fields, attempting to fill in the gaps discussed here, and considering the use of ontological annotations for medical images.

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